

University-Based Data for Good Programs

Academic Data Science Alliance 11/10/21
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University-Based Data for Good Programs

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Human-Centered Design Mentor for the UW Data Science for Social Good Program

A brief introduction to D4G programs:

- What do we mean by “data for good”?
- What is a “Data for Good” program?

Debuting Today

Today's presentation draws from a paper aimed at helping fledgling Data for Good programs

The paper focuses on decision points new programs will encounter in designing their program

The Data for Good Growth Map

Decision Points for Designing a University-Based Data for Good Program

Thirty-six contributors from seventeen universities

University of
Massachusetts
Amherst

IOWA STATE
UNIVERSITY

JOHNS HOPKINS
UNIVERSITY

GEORGETOWN UNIVERSITY

Berkeley
UNIVERSITY OF CALIFORNIA

STANFORD
UNIVERSITY

1789
1899

WARWICK
THE UNIVERSITY OF WARWICK

University of
St Andrews

W
UNIVERSITY of WASHINGTON

VT
VIRGINIA TECH.

THE OHIO STATE UNIVERSITY

What do we mean by “data for good”?

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We position “data for good” as aspirational, relational, dynamic and contested

We view D4G programs as places to advance our understanding and practice of D4G work

- We aim not to naively apply data-intensive methods to questions of profound social consequence, but to reflexively and systematically explore what it takes to do “good” with data
- As places that convene students, faculty, government, non-profit, and industry partners, we view D4G programs as valuable venues to foster dialogue, envision, and explore better practices

Among the programs in our network of contributors

- There is no common single definition of social good across our programs
- Rather each emphasizes different kinds of social impact

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The Data for Good Growth Map

Decision Points for Designing a University-Based Data for Good Program

Our contributors have slightly different ways of framing the good they want to do

Data Science for the **Common Good**, University of Massachusetts Amherst, Center for Data Science

Data Science for the **Public Good**, Iowa State University

Data Science for the **Public Good**, University of Virginia, Biocomplexity Institute

Data Science for the **Public Good**, Virginia Tech, Virginia Cooperative Extension

Data Science for **Social Good**, Carnegie Mellon University

Data Science for **Social Good**, University of British Columbia, Data Science Institute

Data Science for **Social Good**, University of Warwick, Turing Institute

Data Science for **Social Good**, University of Washington, eScience Institute

Florida Data Science for **Social Good** (FL-DSSG), University of North Florida

Stanford Data Science for **Social Good**, Stanford University

What do we mean by “data for good”?

Projects of Contributing Programs by Thematic Areas through 2020

Public Health	34
Environment & Natural Resources	18
Transportation	18
Planning & Development	17
Education	13
Governance	10
Employment & Workforce	8
Human Services	8
Public Safety	8
Socio-economic Disparities	7
Housing & Homelessness	6
Incarceration & Criminal Justice	4
Disaster Response	3
Energy	3
Infrastructure	3
Innovation	2
Public Information	2
Philanthropy	1
Other	10
Total	175

*The table total is less than the number of projects contributors have actually run.

What do we mean by “data for good”?

D4G programs are envisioned as platforms to foster a range of benefits for

- Partner organizations
- Students
- University community & program leadership
- Broader impacts

What is a Data for Good Program?

DATA FOR GOOD PROGRAMS

Collective Experience

Programs	8
Projects	214
Iterations	30
Students	569

- Relatively new offerings
- Relatively small and intensive
- Offered annually, outside of courses
- Paid internships
- Mostly in summer

Home	Start	Session length (weeks)	Frequency	Students-to-date	2019 students	Projects
CMU	2013	12	Annual	300	40	100
UVA	2014	10	Annual	70	12	55
UW	2015	10	Annual	78	15	19
UBC	2016	14	Annual	40	12	12
UNF	2017	12	Annual	24	11	12
UMASS	2019	12	Annual	16	16	6
Stanford	2019	10	Annual	8	8	2
Warwick	2019	12	Annual	33	33	8

2020 survey results: Activity of 8 contributing D4G programs through 2019

COMMON PROGRAM CHARACTERISTICS

- University-hosted
- Educate students
- Project & team based
- Use data science techniques
- Integrate stakeholders
- Intend a social impact

COMMON
PROGRAM
CHARACTERISTICS
UNIVERSITY HOSTED

University-hosted D4G programs are built around the desire to advance the trifecta **missions of education, service, and research.**

This distinguishes these programs from data for good work situated elsewhere.

**COMMON
PROGRAM
CHARACTERISTICS
EDUCATE STUDENTS**

Students served

Common across programs

- Come from a variety of disciplines and backgrounds
- Must have a demonstrated interest in social good
- Must have an interest in doing collaborative interdisciplinary science

Predominates

- Mostly graduate

Varies between programs

- Accept student from multiple be universities
- Support provided beyond stipend
- Level of prior data science and programming experience

COMMON
PROGRAM
CHARACTERISTICS
EDUCATE STUDENTS

D4G program are popular with students,
appealing to a wide variety of students including
those underrepresented in STEM

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Predominates

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**Varies between
programs**

- Can be from other universities
- Support provided beyond stipend
- Level of prior data science and programming experience

COMMON
PROGRAM
CHARACTERISTICS
EDUCATE STUDENTS

A distinct and complementary
internship/fellowship offering

Common across
programs

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Predominates

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**Varies between
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- Can be from other universities
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COMMON
PROGRAM
CHARACTERISTICS
EDUCATE STUDENTS

Graduate students predominate

Common across
programs

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COMMON
PROGRAM
CHARACTERISTICS
EDUCATE STUDENTS

Programs vary on whether they accept students from other universities and the types of support they provide to them

Students served

Common across programs

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- Must have a demonstrated interest in social good
- Must have an interest in doing collaborative interdisciplinary science

Predominates

- Mostly graduate

Varies between programs

- Can be from other universities
- Support provided beyond stipend
- Level of prior data science and programming experience

COMMON
PROGRAM
CHARACTERISTICS
EDUCATE STUDENTS

D4G programs can be tailored to students with different levels of prior data science and programming experience

Common across programs

Students served

- Come from a variety of disciplines and backgrounds
- Must have a demonstrated interest in social good
- Must have an interest in doing collaborative interdisciplinary science

Predominates

- Mostly graduate

Varies between programs

- Can be from other universities
- Provide visas and other support
- Level of prior data science and programming experience

COMMON
PROGRAM
CHARACTERISTICS
PROJECT & TEAM BASED

Project and team based work is
foundational to D4G programs

COMMON
PROGRAM
CHARACTERISTICS
PROJECT & TEAM BASED

UNIVERSITY of WASHINGTON

eScience Institute
DATA SCIENCE FOR SOCIAL GOOD

Students teams
are supported by
technical,
research, and
project mentors
plus admin staff

**Developing Ensemble Methods for Initial
Districting Plan Evaluation**

Katherine Chang
Fellow

Michael Souffrant
Fellow

Rowana Ahmed
Fellow

Ryan Goehring
Fellow

Chris Salazar
Fellow

Delaney Glass
Fellow

Lamar Foster
Fellow

Mahader Tamene
Fellow

Daryl DeFord
Project Lead

Bernease Herman
Data Science Lead

Vaughn Iverson
Data Science Lead

Jennie Romich
Project Lead

Jose Hernandez
Data Science Lead

Valentina Staneva
Data Science Lead

**Geography, Equity, and the Seattle \$15
Minimum Wage Ordinance**

DSSG Program Leadership

Sarah Stone
Program Director

Anissa Tanweer
Program Chair

Emily Keller
Program Coordinator

Dharma Dalley
HCD Mentor

Noah Benson
Data Scientist-at-Large

Jenny Holcomb
Office Coordinator

COMMON PROGRAM CHARACTERISTICS PROJECT & TEAM BASED

**Students,
faculty, and
partners
wear different
hats across
programs**

Program & Project Roles

- **Students:** fellows, interns, technical mentors, PIs, research mentors, project leads, project managers, administrative staff
- **Faculty:** mentors, project leads, PIs, Project Client Liaison, program admin, project admin
- **Partners:** clients, sponsors, stakeholders, project leads, trainers, mentors
- **Program-specific roles:** Project manager, technical support staff, human-centered design mentor

COMMON
PROGRAM
CHARACTERISTICS
PROJECT & TEAM BASED

Rich learning environments:
Project and team based work is augmented by
a number of other teaching modalities.

Many teaching modalities

- Project and team based
- Formal (e.g. tutorials, lectures)
- Informal (e.g. one-on-one mentoring)
- Discussion based (e.g. facilitated conversations)

COMMON
PROGRAM
CHARACTERISTICS
USE DATA SCIENCE
TECHNIQUES

Real-world projects enable deep engagement with core data science concepts, skills, and practices

Reproducibility

Version Control

Documentation

COMMON PROGRAM CHARACTERISTICS

USE DATA SCIENCE TECHNIQUES

Data Science Skills

- Data science tools
- Computer programming
- Version control/Reproducibility

Core Science Skills

- Quantitative methods training
- Qualitative methods training

Public Scholarship

- Science Communication/Presentation
- Design

Integrative learning:

Data science skills are employed in concert with other skills, concepts and practices also essential to project success

Applying Science to Public Interest

- Stakeholder engagement
- Domain area knowledge
- Ethics

Science through Teamwork

- Project management
- Team development/Collaboration
- Professional/Career development

COMMON
PROGRAM
CHARACTERISTICS
USE DATA SCIENCE
TECHNIQUES

Given the short duration, programs must choose which stages of the D4G workflow to support.

What stages of the Data for Good workflow will you support?

COMMON
PROGRAM
CHARACTERISTICS
USE DATA SCIENCE
TECHNIQUES

D4G project can be successfully centered around any part the Data for Good workflow

COMMON
PROGRAM
CHARACTERISTICS
USE DATA SCIENCE
TECHNIQUES

E.g. a D4G project may focus on helping a project partner to articulate a research question & “data discovery”

What stages of the Data for Good workflow will you support?

COMMON
PROGRAM
CHARACTERISTICS
USE DATA SCIENCE
TECHNIQUES

Or a D4G project may focus on making existing data science software more user friendly and more accessible

**COMMON
PROGRAM
CHARACTERISTICS
USE DATA SCIENCE
TECHNIQUES**

If the goal is for students to spend most of their time modeling with shared results at the end...

**COMMON
PROGRAM
CHARACTERISTICS
USE DATA SCIENCE
TECHNIQUES**

... then prior preparation is needed

Before

- Research question
- Research plan
- Intervention plan
- Ready-to-use data

During

After

- Integrate program deliverables into an intervention

**COMMON
PROGRAM
CHARACTERISTICS**
INTEGRATE
STAKEHOLDERS

D4G programs substantively
integrate stakeholders

COMMON
PROGRAM
CHARACTERISTICS
INTEGRATE
STAKEHOLDERS

D4G programs substantively integrate stakeholders

- For educational purposes and to strengthen project outcomes, programs are strongly committed to enabling students to engage directly with stakeholders, particularly project partners.
- Project partners are typically government or non-profit organizations. People from industry and foundations are sometimes also part of the mix.
- Generally, there is a fair amount of engagement between program leads and project partners for project preparation before the program starts.

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COMMON
PROGRAM
CHARACTERISTICS
INTEND A SOCIAL BENEFIT

To effect a social benefit
it is essential that D4G programs:

- Forge strong partnerships
- Select strong projects

COMMON
PROGRAM
CHARACTERISTICS
INTEND A SOCIAL BENEFIT

Consensus considerations for selecting D4G projects

A viable data science project:

- Structured around a research question
- Involve analytic tasks (as opposed to just data engineering or data cleaning)
- Ready-to-use data-in-hand*

Of potential social benefit:

- Strong rationale for why and how the project will make a positive social impact
- Ethical concerns have been carefully considered
- Viability and sustainability of the intervention beyond the D4G program

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University-Based Data for Good Programs

To learn more...

https://bit.ly/Data4Good_GrowthMap

You are invited:

Creating a University-Based Data for Good Program: A Decision Points Workshop

Online workshop

Four 2 hour sessions between
January 14 to February 4, 2022

https://bit.ly/Data4Good_Workshop

UNIVERSITY *of* WASHINGTON

eScience Institute

DATA SCIENCE FOR SOCIAL GOOD

Thank you

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